

TechConnect Capstone:

An Innovative Work-
Based Learning
Opportunity for
Underserved Computer
Science Students

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Executive Summary

This report details findings of an evaluation of the TechConnect Capstone at Green River College where mentors from industry lead groups of underserved computer science students through an open-source software project, creating an innovative work-based learning opportunity.

Internships during computer science (CS) programs are vital in helping college students secure high-paying jobs in the tech industry upon graduation. However, internships are often rife with inequity, making it difficult for adult learners, lower income students, and other minoritized populations to access these coveted roles.

To bring vital work-based learning to their CS students, Green River College (GRC), Mentors in Tech (MinT), and CodeDay collaborated to develop a new work-based learning model, TechConnect Capstone (TCC). With TCC, CS students work in teams on an open-source software project and are paired with mentors, who are currently professionals in tech fields. Mentors guide students as they work through their open-source projects, helping students solve problems, adopt workplace-appropriate solutions and approaches to problems, and keep pace in their work progress.

This brief provides a developmental evaluation of the TCC model. The goal of the evaluation was to understand: (a) In what ways, if at all, the TCC model has been impactful for students and staff; (b) in what ways, if at all, the project had contributed to equitable outcomes for underserved populations; and (c) in what ways the TCC model can be improved.

Through the evaluation, we learned that students found the TCC projects relevant, particularly in terms of communication, teamwork, project management, and developing computer language proficiency. All students shared that they felt better prepared for a job having participated in the TCC model and more prepared to tackle the job market after the capstone project course. This mode of internship was also helpful to adult students and those who may not have otherwise been able to complete traditional internships. Additionally, faculty and staff found that using open-source projects over traditional employer internships was a key for the TCC model's success, particularly because of the way the open-source projects simulate a workplace experience. They also stressed the importance of mentors in the TCC model because of the structure and feedback they provide. Instructors also saw growth in students, including students' confidence and engagement in the project. We find that the TCC model has shown effectiveness at GRC. TCC gives students real-world experience in new software, in working with a collaborative, professional team, and in learning methods that are of a workplace caliber. This mentored, open-source project model might overcome some of the challenges associated with traditional internships while still providing valuable experience and contacts, especially for underserved students and adult learners.

Some challenges also surfaced, including working adult students sharing it was sometimes difficult to dedicate the appropriate amount of time to the project to get the most out of the experience. Faculty and staff shared challenges with assessment, scale, and sustainability, including the ability of the TCC model to weather faculty, administrative, and/or mentor turnover.

A goal of this evaluation was to understand how the TCC model contributed to equitable outcomes for underserved student populations. A longer study, tracking graduates' job placement, income, and other factors, is needed for us to fully gain insight into this question. However, some factors contributing to equity surfaced, including preliminary promising student outcomes, the use of stipends as compensation for students, students' ample access to mentors, and flexibility in the open-source projects.

Background & Methods

Purpose

Internships during computer science (CS) programs are vital in helping college students secure high-paying jobs in the tech industry upon graduation (Strada, 2024). However, COVID-19 left graduating students a suboptimal job market. Opportunities for internships were down by nearly 50 percent (Stansell, 2020a), and job openings for pandemic graduates were down over 60 percent from pre-pandemic rates (Stansell, 2020b). Further, internships that are available are often rife with inequity, making it difficult for adult learners, lower-income students, and other minoritized populations to access these coveted roles (Francisco, 2020; Singer, 2023; Strada, 2023). In addition, students at smaller and less well-known institutions have a particularly difficult time accessing work-based learning opportunities for a variety of reasons, though they are the population that might benefit most (Hang et al., 2023). Such trends were particularly alarming at Green River College in Puget Sound, a geographic region of Washington state where well-paying tech jobs anchor the economy.

In response to these realities, and in an effort to best prepare CS students for a competitive tech industry workforce upon graduation, Green River College (GRC), Mentors in Tech (MinT), and CodeDay collaborated to develop a new work-based learning model, TechConnect Capstone (TCC). Through TCC, the collaborators hoped to “increase the number of students who participate in internships as well as provide students with access to experiential learning opportunities that provide similar value to students as a traditional industry internship” (Hang et al., 2023).

With TCC, CS students work in teams on an open-source software project and are paired with mentors, who are currently professionals in tech fields. Mentors guide students as they work through their open-source projects, helping students solve problems, adopt workplace-appropriate solutions and approaches to problems, and keep pace in their work progress. Students spend six hours weekly on projects in class with faculty and at least four hours weekly collaborating with teammates and meeting with their mentors. Students are paid stipends for out-of-class work at no less than the state’s minimum wage (~\$15/hour), ensuring low-income, working students can participate (Menezes et al., 2022).

About the organizations

Green River College (GRC) is a public community college in Puget Sound, Washington and federally recognized as a minority-serving institution (MUREP, 2023). Its Information Technology department offers two- and four-year tech degrees and received the Aspen Institute’s 2020 Excellence and Equity in Community College STEM award (LeRoi-Schmidt, 2022). Green River is one of 187 community colleges in the country to offer bachelor’s degrees (CCBA et al., 2024).

CodeDay is a non-profit organization that provides opportunities in STEM for high school and college students. It is the creator of CodeDay Labs, an open-source internship program that pairs students with industry professionals as project mentors as students work on an open-source software project (Hang et al., 2023).

Mentors in Tech (MinT) is a nonprofit that helps tech students at smaller, less well-known, accessible, and affordable colleges navigate and launch their careers through structured mentoring programs (Mentors in Tech, n.d.).

About Open Source Projects and the TCC Collaboration

For TCC, MinT and CodeDay recruit and train industry mentors and work with faculty to identify appropriate open-source projects for students. Open-source projects are defined as “an industry engagement experience in which students work on a new or existing software project, licensed under an open-source license” (Menezes et al., 2022). Such projects “allow for students to make open source contributions and project experience to be visible and shareable on their resumes, in interviews, and their portfolios/public profiles (e.g. GitHub, LinkedIn)” (Hang et al., 2023).

The TCC model has three components of a comprehensive work-based learning program: (1) aligned classroom and workplace learning; (2) application of academic, technical, and employability skills in a work setting; and, (3) support from classroom or workplace mentors. TCC embeds “capstone” projects within an upper-division two-course, 10 credit hour sequence in GRC’s Bachelor of Applied Science in Software Development degree program.

To find mentors, MinT relies on its extensive network and calls out to industry partners and professionals to find those who might be interested in serving as mentors. Mentors typically have 10 or more years of experience and often manage teams in their work roles. They’re often working at companies like Apple, Amazon, Microsoft, or other large tech companies. MinT shares the scope of their involvement as mentors, including hours and workload. Once industry professionals self-select to serve as mentors, they partake in an onboarding session and trainings, which includes setting expectations for their commitment and training around how to best support students.

MinT then identifies open-source projects that are interesting, meaningful, and achievable when considering the students’ skill level. MinT brings these projects to instructors who also assess the projects for suitability and alignment with student skills and time commitment and who present the project options to students. Students ultimately get to select their open-source project.

Students assemble in groups of 3–5 and work with three mentors. The mentors often have a direct connection with the open-source community, which helps them guide students through the work.

Student groups meet with their mentors 1–3 times a week, with most groups meeting formally twice a week and informally more often through communications channels for questions and troubleshooting. Additionally, students meet in class with instructors twice a week. Overall, students are expected to spend four hours in class and around 10 hours outside of class on the TCC model each week.

About the evaluation

Following two years of cohorts, our team conducted a developmental evaluation of the work-based learning model TechConnect Capstone (TCC), developed in collaboration with GRC, MinT, and CodeDay. The goal of the evaluation was to understand: (a) In what ways, if at all, the TCC model has been impactful for students and staff; (b) in what ways, if at all, the project had contributed to equitable outcomes for underserved populations; and (c) in what ways the TCC model can be improved.

Framework/Perspectives

Importance of internships

Internship experience plays a critical role in the tech workforce, with work and internship experience being some of the most cited considerations when hiring a tech professional (Stepanova et al., 2021). A report from Strada Education Foundation found that students who completed an internship were “more confident in their ability to communicate their skills and experiences to potential employers than those who have not participated in internships” (2023).

Inequities in internship opportunities

However, many internships and other work-based learning opportunities are rife with inequity (Francisco, 2020). Research (Strada, 2023) has found that “70 percent of first-year students expect to have internships, yet fewer than half of seniors report that they have had one” (para. 7). Part of this asymmetry is that internships are often unpaid, making it difficult or impossible for lower income learners, working learners, or adult learners with caretaking obligations to participate (Francisco, 2020). Students of color, particularly Black and Latine students, are also “significantly less likely” to participate in internship opportunities (Strada, 2023).

Further, students applying to internships who attended “lesser-known public universities said they felt at a disadvantage compared with their peers” who attended more well-known institutions (Singer, 2023). In addition, some research (Van Noy & Jacobs, 2012) indicates that employers have more negative perceptions of community college graduates than their university counterparts. These perceptions add barriers for community college students when they enter the job market, but community college baccalaureate research (Soler & Bragg, 2015) has shown that work-based learning, such as internships, can improve employers’ perceptions of community college students.

Another major factor that prevents students from participating in internships is low self-efficacy. In a qualitative study of 533 undergrads, low self-efficacy was the largest identified theme among students who did not get an internship (Kapoor & Gardner-McCune, 2020).

Theory of Change

Considering both the urgent need for work-based learning opportunities and the inequities often at play with such opportunities, innovative approaches like the TCC model can help provide students with high-quality and more-equitably accessible internship opportunities. Internships provide students with experience working with various software programs in diverse settings, giving them both high-quality content for their resumes and anecdotal examples that they can share in the interview process (Hang et al., 2023). This model circumvents many of the challenges that come with finding traditional internships, especially at colleges without the name-recognition and resources to develop labor-intensive internship programs and partnerships.

Particularly, CodeDay adapted Betz and Hackett’s career decision self-efficacy framework (1981) when designing the program, creating opportunities for students to gain:

(a) Performance accomplishments: The program simulates a real internship, working with industry mentors and leading to software contributions used by tens of thousands of users.

(b) Vicarious learning: The program finds mentors who are not subject experts in the area students are contributing to, thereby modeling various techniques students can use to overcome technical challenges.

Modes of Inquiry

To study the TCC model, we used a developmental evaluation approach. Developmental evaluation “supports development of innovation and adaptation in dynamic environments” (Patton 2011). Developmental evaluation is appropriate for work (a) that is innovative in design and (b) that tackles complex circumstances (Patton, 2011). This project employed an innovative approach to work-based learning in the tech industry through meaningful mentorship and open-source projects, satisfying part (a), and was born in response to the COVID crisis and rampant inequities in the field, certainly complex circumstances (b). In such conditions, developmental evaluation can be beneficial in testing and improving iterations and surfacing issues along the course of the project (Patton, 2011).

Data Sources

The data corpus for this developmental evaluation included: (a) qualitative interviews with participating faculty, staff, and students; (b) artifacts, including student demographic questionnaires, program descriptions, and other written material related to the TCC model; and (c) quantitative data of student demographics and earnings outcomes collected by the Washington State Board for Community and Technical Colleges.

Two cohorts of students who participated in the TCC model were interviewed toward the end of their respective terms. Students were interviewed in five groups, based on their team projects, with 18 total students participating. Of the 18 students, 9 were aged 25 or older, and seven students were career changers. Three of the interviewees were military veterans, and about one quarter of the group identified as female.

Also interviewed were a MinT employee and two faculty members at GRC, one who designed the program and administers the project and another who is the lead course instructor. For all interview sessions, a semi-structured interview protocol was used.

Interviews were recorded and transcribed using a transcription service. Using an open-coding structure, the interviews were coded and analyzed using a computer assisted qualitative data analysis software, MAXQDA. From these codes, we began sorting and aggregating codes into major themes. We engaged in an iterative process while remaining close to the data. Overall, we followed Robert Yin’s (2016) approach for disassembling data (i.e., creating open codes), reassembling data (i.e., categorical coding and looking for intersections of open codes), and interpreting data (i.e., drawing out themes from the coded data).

Findings

In what ways, if at all, has the TCC model been impactful for students and faculty?

Impact for Students

The students found the TCC projects relevant, particularly in terms of communication, teamwork, project management, and developing computer language proficiency. All students shared they felt better prepared for a job having participated in the TCC model and more prepared to tackle the job market after the capstone project course. This mode of internship was also helpful to adult students and those who may not have been otherwise able to complete a traditional internship.

Content of course

Students shared several aspects of the content of the course that they found impactful. They felt that the work was challenging in a way that simulated a workplace experience and that the projects helped them understand an industry standard. They found the open-source projects to be relevant, particularly in teaching them programs and languages that they would go on to encounter in the workplace. Two students shared that working on this project motivated them to work on other open-source projects in their free time, which they believed would prepare them even more for the workforce and help them round out their resume.

Relationships with mentors and peers

Every student group expressed satisfaction with the teamwork and communication of their peer team, citing it is a positive part of their experience. Students believed that such teamwork likely mimicked a workplace environment.

The students also cited their mentors as being incredibly helpful, opening doors on a technical and professional level. One student described getting feedback from their mentor, a Google employee, as “mind-blowing” and shared that the mentor had invited them to a Google forum. Mentors were found to provide insightful feedback and support, especially in new software programs that the students were unfamiliar with. Students expressed that mentors were generous with their time, helping students during office hours, regularly scheduled meetings, and via chat seemingly at any time of day. Many students explained how the mentors would break down tasks into manageable steps, explaining how to complete their tasks in ways students could understand. A student shared:

I really liked about one of the mentors [is that they said]: 'If you don't know anything, like that's fine. You know, just say you don't know, so we can help you guide through it.' That kind of helps out, you know? 'Cause sometimes, especially if we're expecting an industry standard, you don't wanna feel dumb for not knowing anything. But [the mentors] are quite open. 'If you don't know anything, just let us know.'

Students also expressed satisfaction with their mentors' high expectations. One student said that working with a mentor was analogous to working with a senior engineer at a job. Students realized early on that the mentors were going to hold them to industry standards. When students weren't meeting that standard, mentors let them know. One student described a conversation with their mentor:

[My mentor] said something like, you find your Mendoza line, which is basically you find like the bare minimum to do to coast. And I heard that and I was like, yeah, okay. Fine. So the thing with it is because in class, I could do all that as sloppy as I wanted. All that matters [was] I just turned it in and that was done. But because I'm working with people with industry experience who would expect me to be as professional as they are, it's a really good experience to be able to hammer that out and have someone be like, Hey, you can't do that. You have to follow these rules.

Similarly, another student shared how their mentor motivated them to more substantially engage in the work. The student recounted:

I was pulled aside [by my mentor] just to kind of be like, 'Hey, what's going on?' He said something like, 'Yeah, so are you alright? 'Cause you never show up to office hours or troubleshooting. So I have to assume pretty much either that you're really smart, you understand everything you're doing, or you're not putting your 100% into this.

This conversation was the push the student needed to engage more fully with the work.

Workforce Preparation

Students believed that their TCC experience made them more prepared to apply to and interview for jobs. They shared that working on open-source projects and being able to put their experience with programs like GitHub and Python on their resume and LinkedIn would be positive for their job prospects, as employers like to see this kind of experience in prospective employees. Students said that they can also link their name to the open-source project they worked on and could then explain their contribution in an interview, something they found to be positive for their future job search. A student stated:

If interviewers asked about it, I actually have a... It's like a really credible real-world project that I can actually talk about and talk about contributions I've made. So I think if I get an interview and they ask me like, 'Hey, tell me about a time you were in a difficult situation,' I can talk about that for a really long time.

One student recounted how their mentor knew from his experience in the workforce that the TCC experience would help students: "[Our mentor] told us it would be a good opportunity to work on an open-source project, because hiring managers like to see their employees have experience on open-source projects. [They said] people who had experience on open-source projects usually have 50% more chance to get in to get their job. Yeah, that was cool to hear."

Students thought their experience of working on an open-source project alongside mentors also mimicked the work environment. A student explained: “Being able to work with mentors on a standard industry level, I think that definitely will come in handy doing interviews and getting a job hopefully in the future.” Another student agreed, sharing:

There's a lot of code here that is written by someone else and we don't have that initial understanding of the code ourselves, so there's an added challenge of sort of going in and understanding that code, which I think is really helpful because I agree that's probably something we're gonna encounter on the workplace, 'cause I doubt we're gonna be like we writing every single thing from the ground up, we're probably gonna be contributing to the existing systems.

Overall, students expressed hope and optimism that their TCC experience was better preparing them to interview and secure a job in the industry.

Challenges for Students

Personal Challenges

Students expressed some challenges with the open-source project, including limitations in the timing they had to work on it. Students shared that they worked on the project as little as two hours a week and up to 15 or more hours. However, not all students felt like they could dedicate the appropriate amount of time for the task. One student, who works full-time, shared that the project would be more impactful if they had more time:

The timing we can put into it sometimes is not as much as I feel like I want. If it's just a capstone where you're taking the class alone and you're not working full-time too, maybe it would be even more better because then you have the time to really dive deep and you can spend, like, these six hours a day to really dive into some of the materials and look into how to do stuff properly instead of just skim it, get like the beginner style of it, submit it.

Time spent weekly on the project seemed to reflect overall satisfaction. Students who reported spending six or more hours a week on the open-source project seemed more satisfied overall with the experience, compared to students who reported working on it for fewer hours.

Students also shared that owning the right technology to support the open-source project was sometimes a challenge, particularly when it came to storage. A student shared:

When you build a project, it takes up around like 60 gigabytes, so it takes up a lot of space on my computer. Unfortunately, I kind of cheaped out [my] laptops, so that [space issues] has kind of been a little bit of a challenge for me. Recently we've been working on trying to find another way of doing it, apparently if we run it through Docker, some other people had a success in having it not take up quite as much space, and I've been sort of investigating how to get that working.

Good Struggle with Coursework

Students also shared challenges—and ultimately a good struggle—with the coursework. For instance, many students expressed that the open-source work is very challenging, especially as they try to reach an industry standard with their work. While students appreciated the challenge, it could still be overwhelming. A student explained:

They are expecting us to maintain industry standards, as it should be expected. It can get a bit overwhelming sometimes, 'cause we're still not there yet. Industry wise, we have done Capstone projects and then like a lot of projects, but in the school, which weren't really industry based. So like we're still adapting and it's for the better though.

Other students corroborated that coursework up until this experience had not quite prepared them for the high expectation of industry-standard work. A student described this:

There's been a lot of stuff with using GitHub, and I mean, no shade on this program, but we haven't learned how to use those tools in a very in-depth way, or at least nothing very formal. It's sort of been something we've been learning alongside the rest of our classes, but we don't have the most formal training and then using those tools. And so sometimes I feel like my mentors will kind of assume that I'll understand a lot of the jargon they're using.

Related, students explained that sometimes mentors did not understand their skill level at the beginning of the project. One group explained that their mentors encouraged them to ask questions, but they felt uninformed to the point that they did not know what questions to ask. Students also cited that mentors would use jargon they were unfamiliar with or would assume that students were experts in programs like Python. One student group shared that this caused an issue in part because the students did not communicate their skill level early enough to their mentor. The group explained:

At first one of [the] mentors thought we had like five years experience of Python, but actually we did not have that much experience. We only had like maybe half a year of experience. So his expectation was too high on us. He thought we could do anything without their help. And then we started talking about this problem with him. And finally, he realized, oh, you guys are not experts in this field.

Although the mentors' understanding of students' skills was often cited as a challenge, students shared that they overcame this challenge by communicating more with their mentors about their skill level:

It took a while longer than it probably should have because we didn't straight up say like, we don't know what we're doing quite yet. And that kind of caused some hiccups, but if we communicated a bit better at the beginning, I feel like that wouldn't have been as bad.

Students also shared that reaching an industry standard with their work meant making slower progress than they were used to. A student explained: "[The work] feels a lot more methodical, and a lot slower, which is really weird because I feel like I should be working at a faster pace, but it's actually not possible."

Students came to realize that the slower pace is similar to what they'd experience in the workplace. One student shared this realization: "I kind of realized too, like things move a lot slower. Things move a lot... You do a lot smaller increments of things in the workplace. And so I'm actually, I'm happy with the progress that I've made so far."

Mentors helped students feel better about the slow pace. A student described a time when they went to their mentor with worries that they were taking too long on the work: "I went to them and was like, 'I'm freaking out because it's been taking me two weeks to get this environment set up.' And they're like, 'Yeah, I don't think it's ever taken me less amount of time.'"

Further, faculty shared that this kind of struggle and slower pace is part of the design of the program, which is discussed more in the next section.

Impact for Faculty and Staff

Faculty and staff found using open-source projects over traditional employer internships was a key for the TCC model's success, particularly because of the way the open-source projects simulate a workplace experience. They also stressed the importance of mentors in the TCC model because of the structure and feedback they provide. Instructors saw growth in students, including students' confidence and engagement in the project.

Open-source Projects

Faculty and staff highlighted that focusing the work of the capstone on open-source projects, rather than working directly with an employer, was a significant benefit to the TCC model. One participant described open-source projects, conducted on a team and with mentors "as authentic as it gets" when it comes to workforce experience. They shared that the experience gained from open-source projects is more relevant to future work, carries more weight on resumes and with prospective employers, and has more of an impact on the field than traditional employer-based internships. An instructor shared the alignment of the MinT project to workplace experience: "There is oversight at every step, which from what we see is also very indicative of the workplace. A student is not given free reign and artistic decisions. They are narrowed in on a very specific scope on a very small level."

Importance of Mentors: Structure and Feedback

Faculty and staff also described the open-source projects with mentors as more structured than traditional employer-based internships. Instructors shared that students

get more feedback, including more timely feedback, when working with mentors: "It's really difficult for us as instructors to keep tabs on all of the projects. Some projects will go sideways and we won't know until the next time a student presents, which may be a month away." Mentors change this. Because students are meeting with their mentors multiple times a week, they're helped to get unstuck or on the right path faster. Instructors see the pace of help as mimicking workplace culture compared to school culture: "Work culture is like, 'Hey, don't get stuck for too long. Let's bring it to the team and let's work it out if there's an issue.' School culture is like, 'Well, make sure you try and do everything you can before before you ask questions.'"

An instructor noted that getting feedback from someone other than the teacher is also key to students' learning process. They shared:

It's feedback coming from an outside source that's often echoing things that [students] get in the classroom over the quarters that they've been with us. [When it comes from mentors], it's real then, like there's certain things that I as an instructor cannot get across to a student that only a project really will.

The quality of the students' work is also held to a higher standard because of the mentors' feedback. An instructor explained:

There's just a high level of scrutiny, which is something that we can't really duplicate for 40 students all at once. As an instructor, I can't be on top of 40 different tasks all the time. But in the MinT projects, there is a lot of oversight and a lot of structure and some measures of correctness along almost every step.

Student Confidence and Engagement

Instructors also noted a change in students' confidence over the course of the open-source project. Instructors described students communicating with staff, peers, and mentors more confidently as their skillset grew:

I've seen it reflect back even in the non-project environment. Students who I barely hear a peep out of in class, as they're working on these projects, I see that confidence boost starting to happen, like they start speaking more in class and actually are more active in that in-class conversation. I think they're seeing for themselves that this experience is genuine, authentic—it's real, it's not a simulated classroom thing.

The instructors notice that students also seem to not only engage in the project at the onset but to keep up that engagement throughout the experience. With other experiences, instructors described a waning level of excitement and engagement, but with these mentored projects, they see a "consistent level of engagement." One instructor posits this is because students see that their contributions are validated by an industry professional and being utilized in the real world.

Challenges for Faculty and Staff

Faculty and staff noted challenging aspects of the TCC model, including assessing students and issues with scaling and sustainability.

Assessing Students

Instructors shared that they are still continuing to refine how they assess students in efforts to make grades as fair as possible. Difficulty in assessment arises in part because every open-source project is different. An instructor shared:

"We're always trying to find better and clearer assessments. We want the grades to reflect reality as best we can because there's a lot of ambiguity because every project is quite different." They want assessment to incent the right type of engagement, progress, and learning and avoid incenting behavior that detracts from the overall experience, like rushing through a project for completion at the expense of quality.

That said, instructors are on a path forward with assessment. One instructor shared that students are evaluated on three aspects: (1) their technical progress in the assignments, usually evaluated every two weeks; (2) their communications, including being active in communications channels, writing up meeting notes, and staying in touch with their team and mentors; and (3) their efforts in managing the project, including breaking a large project into manageable tasks, making efforts to look up how to solve problems, and taking part in programming activities with other students or their mentors. Although this three-pronged evaluation leaves room for interpretation, it is a good start for evaluating a varied experience.

Scaling and Sustainability

When it comes to scaling and sustaining the TCC model to other institutions, several challenges arise. First, staff indicated that finding mentors for additional institutions could create issues. While GRC has never struggled to find mentors, it is not lost on instructors that the experience hinges on mentors' participation.

They also shared that faculty buy-in creates issues in scale and sustainability. One staff member shared that it's critical for faculty to realize students need to be competitive in the job market, and experiences like the TCC model really does a lot in giving students a competitive edge. However, they acknowledge that "it takes a certain type of faculty to be that invested in the career outcomes of their students," something that GRC has been lucky to find in their instructors but could be difficult at other institutions.

Similarly, faculty turnover is a threat to scale and sustainability. One interviewee illustrated that turnover in faculty and administration can considerably derail TCC efforts. New faculty need time to acclimate to their new roles, their teaching load, and navigating a new institution, so the TCC experience gets bumped down the list of priorities. The interviewee shared, "Every time [turnover] happens, it feels like we lose a year."

Findings

In what ways, if at all, has the project contributed to equitable outcomes for underserved populations?

A goal of this evaluation was to understand how the TCC model contributed to equitable outcomes for underserved student populations. A longer study, tracking graduates' job placement, income, and other factors, is needed for us to fully gain insight into this question. However, within the confines of this evaluation, some factors contributing to equity surfaced, including preliminary promising student outcomes, the use of stipends as compensation for students, ample access to mentors, and flexibility in the open-source projects.

Stipends

In the TCC model, student participants are paid stipends for out-of-class work at no less than the state's minimum wage (~\$15/hour), totaling to \$500. This compensation was included to help ensure low-income, working students could participate in the experience. In the interviews, students cited the financial compensation for the project as helpful but unexpected; many students indicated it was not a deciding factor for participating in the program, although it did help encourage more robust efforts in the course. Compensation is an important aspect of work-based learning opportunities; research shows that students who have "a paid internship during their undergraduate education have higher-paying jobs after graduation, even when accounting for differences in pay based on field of study, gender, and race/ethnicity" (Strada, 2024b). Although students weren't always aware of the stipend and didn't necessarily make their decision to participate based on the stipend, it remains an important component for promoting equity within the program, considering how many of the participating students were working adult learners.

Flexible Timing: Access to Mentors

Students cited their satisfaction with their mentors' availability during the open-source project as something that worked well with the program. For example, one group shared that their team was originally only meeting once a week with their mentors, but after they told their mentor that they were struggling to keep up, the mentor added on an extra meeting plus office hours. Another student shared that her mentor was "always answering back to messages. She's very quick to get back to you, which is really helpful." Another mentor went above and beyond to be accessible for help. About this mentor, a student shared: "He's always there. Like he's always there. You wake up and there's some Git notification that he's been working on this at 4:00 AM in the morning. It's crazy that he's always there. And whatever questions you have, you go to him, he has the answers for you."

Having just-in-time access to tutoring and help from a mentor, even outside of normal meeting times, is an important element for equity in education (Floyd et al., 2005). It allows students with work schedules, family commitments, and other constraints on their time to get help in coursework when their schedule allows. It also helps students move forward with the learning experience, helping them get "unstuck" faster and move on with content.

Flexible Timing: Open-Source Projects

The nature of the open-source projects also provides elements of equity not present in traditional internships. In a traditional internship, students or faculty need a strong social or professional network to find employers to host student interns. Traditional internships, especially at larger organizations like Microsoft or Google, can include non-disclosure agreements for the interns, making it difficult for students to describe their internship experience on a resume or in interviews. Last, internships often include smaller, one-off tasks that don't have the scale or impact a prospective employer is looking for in an applicant.

Using open-source projects instead of internships solves such equity issues. First, open-source projects are open to anyone to work on and are not dependent on a social or professional network to gain entry. They have demonstrable impact on the field and are easier to describe or demonstrate to an employer, all factors that make it easier to leverage the experience to apply to and get jobs after graduation.

Open-source projects are also largely self-paced, which students cited as important for their learning and for the realities of their schedules. A student shared: "The thing is like, the open source is not time. There's no deadlines. So you can take your time on an issue and then get all the help that you need from our mentors." Another student described how the self-paced nature helped them navigate a difficult time: "I had a bad week and I didn't do a lot of work, they're like, 'It's okay. You can take your time. It's an open source. It's not like this is the deadline.'" Such flexibility is an important feature of equity, particularly in community college bachelor's programs (Pawlicki et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Recommendations

1

Scale

While we found positive outcomes for GRC, we recommend expanding the model to more sites to fully understand its impact and effectiveness. The original grant proposal sought to test the TCC model's replicability at a public technical college, Lake Washington Institute of Technology (LWTech). However, due to staff turnover and other challenges, this step was not taken. Testing the TCC model at other community and technical colleges is important to understand the scale and viability for replication at other institutions. Further, bringing the TCC model to greater scale will help us to longitudinally understand the impact the TCC model has on equitable outcomes for underserved populations.

2

Sustainability

Faculty described the fragility of programs like TCC, sharing that often such programs are dependent on relationships with specific individuals at colleges and organizations that champion the work. While relationships with such champions are meaningful and effective in the short term, challenges arise when faculty and other staff move into different roles or leave the institution. When faculty and staff leave, it can be difficult to find a new person willing to carry on the TCC work, presenting issues in both sustaining TCC where the program already exists and scaling programs to new institutions. We recommend MinT develop strategies to make TCC and similar models less dependent on willing champions so that its positive impact on students can withstand personnel turnover.

Although there are some issues with sustainability, this type of model is potentially more sustainable than traditional employer-based internship models because of the mentor relationship and the nature of open-source projects. Specifically, MinT and institutions are developing a relationship with a group of mentors who can be followed from company to company, and open-source projects can be continuously sourced and vetted. This alleviates some of the turbulence caused by economic conditions or turnover found in traditional employer relationships.

3

Stipends

Stipends are an important aspect of the equity imperative of this work, but most students expressed that they did not know there was a stipend associated with this experience. Some shared that they only learned about it at the very end of the experience, while others said they had heard mention of a stipend before they joined but then forgot as the experience got started. One student recounted that, when they heard they would be working on an open-source project as part of this course, they remarked, “Great, free labor,” and were later happy to hear that their labor was not free after all. Another student said that, after they were reminded about the stipend, they were more motivated to invest time in their project and do a good job, something they thought mimicked their future workplace.

It is possible that some students might be deterred from self-selecting in for the TCC experience due to similar fears of “free labor” or timing constraints in balancing the open-source project with other job or family obligations and other course work. We recommend more broadly and routinely sharing information about the stipend with prospective and current students. Doing so could draw prospective students who might otherwise be deterred due to workforce or family commitments. Further, reminding current students of the stipend might encourage students to put in more time or effort into the project, thereby improving their experience, learning, and workforce preparation.

Limitations

Interviews with mentors

We were not able to conduct interviews with the participating mentors due to time constraints. Instead, MinT provided us with several videos of mentors discussing their experiences and contributions. Interviews with mentors would help us understand how they experienced the TCC project, share further insights into students' experiences and performance, and overall provide a more holistic view into the program. Future iterations of this work should attempt to bring mentors' experiences into the fold.

Small student groups

This evaluation uses a relatively small student sample size, based on two student cohorts with a total of 18 students. While much can be gleaned from these students' experiences, more can be learned by continuing this program and subsequent evaluation with future cohorts.

Concluding Thoughts

From our developmental evaluation, we find that the TCC model has shown effectiveness at GRC. The TCC model gives students real-world experience in new software, in working with a collaborative, professional team, and in learning methods that are of a workplace caliber. This mentored, open-source project model might overcome some of the challenges associated with traditional internships while still providing valuable experience and contacts, especially for underserved students and adult learners.

To evaluate its merit for replication on a broader scale, it must be tested at multiple colleges with additional mentors and open-source projects. We envision that this pilot of the TCC model and the resulting evaluation can be used by other CS programs as they design innovative and equitable work-based learning opportunities to help students prepare more competitively for the workforce upon graduation.

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